

Corrosion Behavior of High Energy-High Rate Consolidated Graphite/Copper Metal Matrix Composites in Chloride Media

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ABSTRACT

The corrosion behavior of high energy-high rate (HEHR) consolidated particulate reinforced graphite/copper (Gr_p/Cu) metal matrix composites (MMCs) was studied in aerated and deaerated 3.5 wt% sodium chloride solutions using electrochemical techniques, ionic solution analysis, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDX), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) techniques.

The results of the investigation of 1.2, 5, 15, 25, and 40 volume percent Gr_pCu composites showed that the severity of corrosive attack increased with increasing graphite content and in aerated solutions. While the composite samples exhibited uniform corrosion of the copper matrix as well as localized corrosion at the graphite-copper interface, benzotriazole was found to be an effective corrosion inhibitor in minimizing both of those effects.

INTRODUCTION

The future of the basic and hi-tech industries depends on the development and improvement of new materials. For example, many aerospace applications require materials with a high thermal conductivity to reduce component operating temperature and a moderate density to reduce overall system weight [1]. If these new materials, such as metal matrix composites, are to become incorporated into current engineering systems, their corrosion behavior must be determined and understood before exposure to service environments. In the case of metal matrix composites, surface and interfacial phenomena play a critical role in determining the environmental stability of the material.

This research focuses on particulate reinforced graphite copper metal matrix composites. Copper offers excellent thermal conductivity, the second best among the elements, but suffers from low yield strength and stiffness [2]. It is therefore possible to reinforce the copper matrix with a stiffer and lighter material and thereby enhance the yield strength and stiffness. The resulting copper base-metal matrix composites can often offer higher strength-to-weight ratios, higher elastic moduli, reduced thermal expansion, and wider operational temperature ranges than copper or conventional copper alloys.

Particulate reinforced graphite copper metal matrix composites are currently being used as sliding electrical contacts for generator parts in the automotive, utility, and aerospace industries [3]. These electrical contacts transfer current between stationary and moving parts of electrical machinery. Commercially available brush materials capable of transferring large electrical currents through sliding contacts incorporate low temperature binders such as lead or tin to improve the strength and interfacial bonding of the brush material. These binders decrease the conductivity of the electrical contact and tend to melt in high velocity-high current applications,

resulting in decreased conductivity and excessive wear of the electrical contact. For optimum performance, sliding electrical contacts for high velocity-high current applications must demonstrate high conductivity and wear resistance at high sliding interface temperatures [4]. Therefore, binderless graphite reinforced copper composites offer an attractive alternative for high velocity-high current applications [5].

While the focus of this investigation was graphite/copper composites, copper composites in general offer also great potential for marine applications, such as propellers and structural components of missiles, mines, and torpedoes, pump impellers, heat exchangers, pipes, and pipe fittings because of their antifouling characteristics, higher strengths, and lower densities than conventional copper alloys [6]. Also, graphite fiber reinforced copper MMCs in particular, are ideal candidates for high heat flux structures operating at elevated surface temperatures due to their high thermal conductivity, high modulus of elasticity, and moderate density. A potential application of these composites has been identified by McDanel and Diaz as space power system radiator fins [7].

Graphite/copper composites are also of interest as a model composite system. Graphite and copper are mutually insoluble and do not react with one another to form a compound; only a mechanical bond exists between the graphite reinforcement and the copper matrix. Therefore, the goal of this research was to examine the effects of increasing volume percent reinforcement on the corrosion behavior of Gr_p/Cu composites in neutral chloride media.

In terms of corrosion behavior, the corrosion resistance of copper and copper base metal matrix composites in seawater is determined by the nature of a naturally occurring and protective corrosion product film. North and Pryor identified the constituents of this film to be cuprous oxide, cuprous hydroxychloride and cupric oxide [8]. As these oxides form in NaCl solutions, the open circuit potential of copper becomes more noble. In addition, the formation and stability of these oxides is enhanced in the presence of dissolved oxygen. There is one potential problem, however, and that is galvanic corrosion between the matrix and the reinforcement. In this study, special consideration must be given to the graphite-copper interface. Galvanic coupling within the specimen is expected to result in increased localized corrosion rates. In graphite-reinforced copper metal matrix composites, the graphite reinforcement is substantially more noble than the copper matrix, as indicated in the galvanic series of metals and alloys in unpolluted seawater; copper is the anode and the graphite is the cathode [9]. This problem will be addressed in this investigation.

Because of the potential corrosion problems that could arise from the use of copper MMCs, it is necessary to address the issue of corrosion inhibition. Benzotriazole (C₆H₄N₃H) is considered as one of the most effective inhibitors for copper and copper alloys in severe environments [10,11]. It reacts with copper to form a compact chemisorbed polymeric multilayer film of Cu₂C₆H₄N₃ [11,12]. Therefore, this research has focused on the effectiveness of benzotriazole as a corrosion inhibitor for copper MMCs. In particular, the ability of benzotriazole to minimize galvanic corrosion has been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

MATERIALS

The composites studied were manufactured using dendritic copper powders (-325 mesh) and graphite flakes (-230 mesh). Dendritic copper powders are used over spherical powders because the dendritic powders tend to increase the interfacial contact with the graphite reinforcement. This increase in interfacial contact provides a more highly densified microstructure due to more efficient and thorough interfacial heating [13]. HEHR consolidation techniques were utilized to fabricate 1.2, 5, 15, 25, and 40 volume percent Gr_p/Cu composites. HEHR consolidated 100% copper and Electrolytic Tough Pitch (ETP) copper (98.1 wt % Cu) were also used in this study for comparison. All specimens, with exception of the ETP samples, were pressed at 275 MPa during their respective processing techniques and manufactured as circular coupons 22 mm in diameter. ETP copper specimens were cut from a plate of ETP copper. All specimens were ground to a 600 grit surface finish using SiC paper and distilled water as the lubricant. Samples

were subsequently rinsed in distilled water for 30 seconds, air dried, and stored in desiccators prior to microstructural observation and electrochemical testing.

HIGH ENERGY-HIGH RATE PROCESSING

Advances in kinetic energy storage devices have aided in the development of a new approach to powder processing of metal matrix composites. This process involves the internal heating of a composite powder blend through the rapid discharge of a homopolar generator (HPG). An in depth discussion on the fundamental approaches to high energy-high rate processing has been described by Marcus et. al [14,15].

The Gr_p/Cu composites studied in this research were manufactured at the Center for Electromagnetics at The University of Texas at Austin using a 10 MJoule pulsed homopolar generator in conjunction with a modified vertical axis press with an 890 kNewton loading capacity. The important characteristics of high energy-high rate processing are: the short time the compact is at high temperature which reduces the time for internal oxidation; rapid heating and cooling of the composite due to the rapid discharge of a high applied current which maintains a fine microstructure, and microencapsulation of the graphite reinforcement by preferential heating at the graphite-copper interface which results in a dense product without requiring post-processing heat treatments.

MICROSTRUCTURAL EVALUATIONS

Radial and transverse cross sections of the as-processed composite materials were metallographically inspected to evaluate their as-processed microstructures. The quality and homogeneity of the material, specifically in terms of the alignment and distribution of the graphite reinforcement in the copper matrix, were examined. As-polished composite surfaces were examined using SEM to determine the nature of the surface prior to electrochemical testing and to inspect the quality of graphite-copper interfaces of the composite surfaces. The EDX capabilities of the scanning electron microscope were utilized to identify the chemical constituents of the electrode surfaces after immersion in the 3.5 wt% NaCl.

INSTRUMENTATION AND ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCEDURES

All electrochemical tests (E_{CORR} vs time, polarization resistance, and potentiodynamic polarization) were conducted on planar electrodes using an EG&G Model 273 Potentiostat/Galvanostat, EG&G model 342 corrosion software, a five mouth flask, and a flat specimen holder exposing a specified surface area. Tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM standards using a saturated calomel electrode as the reference electrode. All tests were run on at least three identical specimens and average values will be reported.

Electrochemical tests were conducted in 3.5 wt% NaCl solutions prepared prior to each test using reagent grade sodium chloride and distilled water ($pH\ 7.0 \pm 0.2$). Solutions were aerated or deaerated by sparging the solution for a period of one hour preceding and during the test using industrial grade oxygen or nitrogen, respectively. Typical values of the dissolved oxygen concentration in aerated solutions were 10 ppm, whereas the concentration in deaerated solutions averaged 0.5 ppm.

Open circuit potentials were monitored as a function of time for all specimens and the steady-state corrosion potentials were designated as E_{CORR} . Specimens were polarized from 15 mV below to 15 mV above E_{CORR} at a scan rate of 0.1 mV/sec to determine the polarization resistance. The potentiodynamic polarization tests were conducted at a scan rate of 0.2 mV/sec with the scans typically running from -250 mV below E_{CORR} to +800 mV vs SCE. The tests were conducted on identical volume percent Gr_p/Cu electrodes in aerated and deaerated solutions to evaluate the stability of the surface film as well as the effects of dissolved oxygen on film formation. After polarization testing, specimens were rinsed in distilled water for 20 seconds, air dried, and placed in a desiccator for storage. The corroded microstructures were observed by SEM imaging and analyzed by EDX and XRD techniques.

SOLUTION ANALYSIS

After electrochemical testing, test solutions were analyzed for ionic copper and total carbon content. An ion coupled plasma technique was used for the copper analysis and a furnace-Coulometric technique (ASTM D4129) was utilized for the total carbon analysis.

EVALUATION OF BENZOTRIAZOLE AS A CORROSION INHIBITOR

Benzotriazole was evaluated as an inhibitor in 3.5 wt% NaCl solutions at a concentration of 0.2 g/l (200 ppm). Copper MMCs were examined at open circuit potential, during linear polarization and during potentiodynamic anodic polarization.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MICROSTRUCTURAL PROPERTIES

A representative micrograph of the 1.2 vol% graphite composite surface prior to any electrochemical testing is shown in Figure 1. All composite samples displayed relatively uniform distribution of the graphite particles in the copper matrix. However, graphite pullout resulting from metallurgical preparation was evident, particularly in the 40 vol % Gr_p/Cu. The dark areas in the figure are graphite particles and the brighter areas, which are rough in appearance, are surface defects due to graphite pullout. Black areas at the graphite-copper interface are voids where the molten copper did not completely wet the graphite reinforcement. A small amount of porosity is observed in the copper matrix in the form of micron sized voids due to incomplete solidification of the composite during processing. While some voids are present, there is generally good mechanical bonding at the copper/graphite interface. This microencapsulation of the graphite particle leads to a more highly densified composite product. As processed residual porosity measurements ranged from -5 to 7% for Gr_p/Cu HEHR consolidated composites. Low residual porosity values are indicative of sound mechanical bonding at the interface and higher densities. This reduction in porosity for the HEHR composites offers two advantages: one, post-processing heat treatments to reduce the porosity are not required; and two, better bonding at the graphite-copper interface improves wear resistance. Optimum current carrying capability and wear resistance for electrical contacts occur when 6% porosity is observed. HEHR consolidation parameters have been optimized to achieve these properties.

ELECTROCHEMICAL BEHAVIOR

Extensive research has been published on the corrosion behavior of copper and copper alloys in neutral NaCl [8,16,17] Results are mentioned here to provide a basis for evaluating the effects of adding the graphite reinforcement to the copper matrix to create the MMC. In near neutral aqueous environments, cuprous oxide, Cu₂O, is the component of the corrosion product that provides protection for copper and its alloys. For corrosion to occur, copper ions and electrons must diffuse through the cuprous oxide film.

Behavior at E_{corr}

The open circuit corrosion potentials of the specimens reached a steady state value in approximately 2 hours. Since graphite is substantially noble to copper, the free corrosion potentials of these composites would be expected to become more positive as the volume percent of graphite is increased. This trend held true for all of the Gr_p/Cu composites in aerated and deaerated 3.5 wt% NaCl solutions (18). In aerated solutions, the values ranged from about -238 mV vs SCE for the 1.2 vol % graphite composite to about -199 mV vs SCE for the 40 vol % graphite composite. As anticipated, the E_{corr} values were more active (about -20 mV in each case) in the deaerated solution than in the corresponding aerated solution. This electronegative shift results from the inability of the electrode surface to form a continuous protective oxide layer; insufficient dissolved oxygen is present in deaerated solutions to form such an oxide film.

The exposed surfaces of numerous specimens after 4-10 hours immersion in the electrolyte were examined using SEM and the following observations were made:

1. The topography of the electrode surfaces exposed in aerated solutions was not markedly different from those exposed in deaerated solutions.
2. Voids in the composite due to graphite pullout during electrode preparation or surface defects did not act as initiation sites for localized corrosion phenomenon, at least during the 4-10 hours of immersion.
3. Negligible galvanic attack was observed in the 1.2, 5 and 15 vol% Gr_p/Cu composites at their rest potential. Galvanic corrosion between the graphite reinforcement and the copper matrix became more pronounced as the volume percent of graphite and the exposure time increased to 25 and 40 vol%.
4. Cracks emanating from the graphite-copper interface were detected in composites immersed in deaerated and aerated NaCl solutions for 10 hours.

Linear Polarization Behavior

The polarization resistance decreased slightly as the volume percent of graphite increased. This trend held true in both aerated and deaerated 3.5 wt% NaCl. In aerated solution, the values went from 1.4 k-ohm/cm² for the 1.2 vol% graphite composite to 0.6 k-ohm/cm² for the 40 vol% graphite composite.

Potentiodynamic Polarization Behavior

Figure 2 shows the striking similarity between typical polarization curves for the composite specimens and the pure copper specimens (eg HEHR 100% Cu and the ETP Cu). The polarization curve for copper is divided into four regions of behavior: I) the apparent Tafel region; II) the peak current and minimum current region; III) the limiting current region; and IV) the post-limiting current (higher potential) region. The behavior exhibited by the composites is therefore consistent with that of pure copper in chloride media as detailed by Lee and Nobe [16] and Milsev and Metikos-Hukovic [17]. In addition, as with copper, the anodic polarization behavior of the copper composites is dependent on the mass transport-reaction mechanisms of the chloride ions.

Anodic polarization tests of the 15, 25, and 40 vol% Gr_p/Cu specimens exhibited small fluctuations in the anodic current density in the higher potential regions. This behavior seemed to occur when a portion of the composite would pull away from the sample surface, revealing an uncorroded surface, that then acted as a new anodic site. This resulted in a momentary fluctuation in the current density.

Composite specimens which were polarized from E_{corr} to +800 mV_{sce} showed evidence of uniform corrosion of the matrix, initiation of galvanic corrosion at graphite-copper interfaces, and cracking on the surface. Galvanic corrosion resulted in the destruction of the mechanical bond at the interface. Eventually, the entire interface was destroyed due to this attack and some of the graphite reinforcement fell away from the electrode surface, leaving a void in its place. Cracks appeared to originate at the graphite-copper interface and propagate through the matrix, running into other cracks. While galvanic corrosion seemed to be more extensive as the amount of graphite was increased and in the aerated solutions, cracking was more severe in the deaerated solutions. Since the aerated electrolyte is saturated with dissolved oxygen, cuprous oxide may form on the exposed crack tips and crack walls, retarding the propagation of the crack. A greater amount of corrosion product was also observed around the areas of galvanic corrosion and cracking for the specimens polarized in the aerated electrolyte. The high concentration of dissolved oxygen in the electrolyte accelerated oxygen reduction. Galvanic corrosion was therefore accelerated in these specimens, resulting in a larger amount of redeposited corrosion product.

It is interesting to note that the anodic polarization behavior was very similar for all the composites specimens, independent of the condition of the solution. However, E_{corr} values and the cathodic polarization curves varied as a function of aeration or deaeration of the solution.

Solution analysis SEM results revealed that ionic copper was found in all solutions, verifying that copper was oxidized and exfoliation did occur. The presence of graphite in the electrolyte was also verified. This is further evidence of galvanic corrosion; the graphite-copper interface was

degraded and small amounts of graphite fell away from the electrode surface. However, the majority of the graphite reinforcement remained on the surface and was held in place through the accumulation of corrosion products.

Effectiveness of Benzotriazole

In order to examine the effectiveness of benzotriazole, selected composites were tested in 3.5 % NaCl solutions containing 200 ppm benzotriazole. As anticipated, the improvement in corrosion behavior decreased as the vol% of graphite increased. In addition, polarization resistance values for the composites were two to ten times higher in the NaCl solution containing benzotriazole although there was no trend with vol% of composite.

Anodic polarization curves comparing the electrochemical behavior of HEHR 1.2 vol% Gr_P/Cu specimens in aerated 3.5% NaCl with and without 200 ppm benzotriazole are given in Figure 3. In addition to the remarkable decrease in anodic current density, it is also interesting to note that there was about a four fold increase in the polarization resistance with benzotriazole, indicating a reduction in the uniform corrosion rate. Similar improvement was observed even at volume percentages up to 40 vol % graphite. Benzotriazole appears to minimize galvanic corrosion until higher applied potentials are reached. This may be due to the increased stability of the copper matrix. An SEM micrograph of the 1.2 vol% Gr_P/Cu composite after polarization is shown in Figure 4.

As a corrosion inhibitor, benzotriazole seems to be effective in minimizing corrosive attack of the copper matrix and galvanic corrosion at the interface. It may be possible to expand the potential applications of this inhibitor by utilizing optimum concentrations of benzotriazole solutions as pre-treatment for copper MMCs.

CONCLUSIONS

A research program was conducted to assess the corrosion behavior of particulate reinforced Gr_P/Cu metal matrix composites in 3.5 wt% NaCl solutions. The main emphasis of this research was to identify and characterize the corrosion mechanisms occurring in these composites as a function of the volume percent of graphite reinforcement. The results obtained are summarized as:

1. The potentiodynamic polarization curves generated for pure copper electrodes and Gr_P/Cu electrodes are similar and are dominated by the behavior of copper. The four regions of polarization behavior, typical of pure copper, are observed. The change in magnitude of the peak current and minimum current region decreased as the volume percent of graphite increases because less copper is available to participate in the anodic reactions.
2. For a given volume percent reinforcement, the corrosion mechanisms of the HEHR composites are similar, independent of aeration or deaeration of the test solution. The severity of the corrosion of the Gr_P/Cu metal matrix composites increased with increasing graphite content.
3. All composite samples exhibited uniform corrosion and localized galvanic corrosion at the graphite-copper interface. Copper is oxidized and goes into solution and a small amount of graphite is detected in the electrolyte due to galvanic corrosion at the interface.
4. While localized galvanic corrosion degrades the stability of the graphite-copper interface, the majority of the graphite reinforcement remains on the surface and is held in place through the accumulation of a corrosion product consisting mainly of copper chloride•3 copper hydroxide, copper chloride hydroxide, and copper chloride hydrate.
5. Benzotriazole seems to be effective in minimizing corrosive attack of the copper matrix and galvanic corrosion at the interface. It may have potential as a pretreatment for copper MMCs.

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Figure 1. SEM micrograph of an as-polished 1.2 vol% Gr_p/Cu MMC prior to electrochemical testing.

Figure 2. Representative anodic polarization curves for the monolithic and composite materials in aerated 3.5% NaCl.

Figure 3. Anodic polarization curves for the 1.2 vol% Gr_p/Cu MMC in aerated 3.5 wt% NaCl with and without benzotriazole.

Figure 4. SEM micrograph of a 1.2 vol% Gr_p/Cu MMC after polarization to 600 mV vs SCE in aerated 3.5 wt% NaCl + 200 ppm benzotriazole.